
The Role of Textiles in International Trade

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ABSTRACT

A detailed examination of such a topic will be based on a fundamental problem, which will serve as a guiding principle in the presentation of the ideas underpinning the approach. In this case, it concerns the question of the links between international trade and textiles. In other words, what is the role of textiles in international trade ? How do WTO policies regarding textile production and marketing impact developing countries aspiring to development?

Thus, the problem of method is central to all scientific work, as method illuminates hypotheses and determines conclusions. Our approach will be structured, with a few exceptions, around the use of analytical and exegetical methods, as well as comparative methods. This is understood as the analysis, interpretation, and explanation of legal rules, particularly those contained in the various legal texts of the GATT and the WTO.

As for the expected results, trade in textiles and clothing, while less significant than that in agricultural products, is not negligible. Indeed, together (and they are roughly equivalent), they represented 6% of world trade in 1995, or just over \$300 billion. Textiles, unlike agricultural products, were not to be subject to any special treatment under the 1947 General Agreement on Trade (GATT); they were subject to the general law applicable to international trade in goods. However, from the early 1960s onward, they would fall outside the scope of the GATT and become subject to a special legal regime, thus illustrating the phenomenon of "GATT à la carte," so often encountered and which became one of the characteristics of the Geneva institution.¹The Punta del Este Ministerial Conference of September 1986 was tasked with assigning to future multilateral negotiations the responsibility of reintegrating textiles into the GATT framework, with strengthened trade disciplines and a view to trade liberalization. This was achieved through the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATC), one of the multilateral agreements on trade in goods annexed to the Marrakesh Agreement establishing the WTO. Thus, after being removed from the GATT, textiles were to be reintegrated into the WTO at the urgent request of developing countries, which, in exchange for this concession, accepted the inclusion of services and intellectual property in the new integrated trading system established by the Marrakesh Agreements.

The aim will therefore be to study the question of status quo ante, that is to say the Multi-Fiber Agreement (Section I), then the progressive liberalization of textiles with the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (Section II).

KEYWORDS : ATC, GATT, Liberalization, MFA, WTO

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SECTION I : THE STATUS QUO ANTE : THE MULTI-FIBRE AGREEMENT

The trade in textiles and clothing, although less significant than that in agricultural products, is not negligible. Indeed, together (and they are roughly equivalent), they represented 6% of world trade in 1995, or just over 300 billion dollars.

Unlike agriculture, textiles were not to be subject to any special treatment under the General Agreement of 1947; they were subject to the common law applicable to international trade in goods.

¹ CARREAU, D., JUILLARD, P. (2017). International Economic Law, pp 170-175, 6th edition, Dalloz.

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However, from the early 1960s onwards, they would fall outside the scope of the General Agreement and become subject to a special legal regime, thus illustrating the phenomenon of "GATT à la carte," so often encountered and which became one of the characteristics of the Geneva institution.²

The Punta del Este Ministerial Conference of September 1986 was tasked with assigning to future multilateral negotiations the responsibility of reintegrating textiles into the GATT framework with strengthened trade disciplines and a view to trade liberalization. This was achieved through the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATV), one of the multilateral agreements on trade in goods annexed to the Marrakesh Agreement establishing the WTO. Thus, after being removed from the GATT, textiles were to be reintegrated into the WTO at the urgent request of developing countries, which, in exchange for this concession, accepted the inclusion of services and intellectual property in the new integrated trading system established by the Marrakesh Agreements. During the initial period (1948-1961) when textile products were subject to the general rules of the GATT, they sometimes found themselves at the center of trade disputes, particularly under the safeguard clause of Article XIX. Subsequently, specific provisional agreements began to be concluded and gradually expanded. Due to their unique characteristics, these agreements established a legal framework for trade in textiles that differed significantly from the general rules of the GATT.

The first agreement of 1961 dealt only with the international trade of cotton textiles and had a very short duration (a little over a year). The second, entitled "long-term agreement", had a much broader scope both "ratione materiae" since it covered all textile products and "ratione temporis" since it was concluded for renewable three-year periods (it was in fact renewed continuously until 1973).

On that latter date, a "Multi-Fibre Agreement" (MFA) was to take over, to be constantly renewed, and not to expire until January 1, 1995, with the entry into force of the WTO and thus the subsequent Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS). Following its numerous renewals, the MFA eventually covered all international trade in textile products, whether made of cotton, wool, or plant fibers (such as silk), and especially synthetic fibers, even including counterfeit products (counterfeiting having first appeared in the MFA and in international trade law in 1986 at the request of the EEC). Thus, from 1973 onward, international trade in textiles was effectively removed from the general legal framework established by the 1947 General Agreement on Textiles.

First, the economic philosophy governing the AMF was diametrically opposed to that of the GATT. While the latter was steeped in free trade, the former was founded on the idea of "organized" free trade, a phrase favored by the French Prime Minister of the time, Raymond Barre, in 1977. As a consequence of this "organization" of free trade, the AMF legalized bilateral self-limitation agreements between importing and exporting countries of textile products, the latter thus voluntarily agreeing not to flood the markets of the former. These agreements, euphemistically called self-limitation, are the equivalent of quantitative restrictions that dare not speak their name and which are rightly and formally prohibited by the GATT in both 1947 and 1994. Moreover, this technique circumvents the rules for implementing Article XIX, which constitute the safeguard clause of the General Agreement. In the same vein, the AMF contained a precise clause on market disruption, admittedly much more so than the vague content of the analogous provision of the GATT in its article XIX.

Furthermore, the AMF had its own institutional framework. It was administered on a day-to-day basis by a supervisory body that reported to a Textiles Committee composed of all signatories and decided on broad policy directions or acted as an appellate body. Moreover, and most importantly, these bodies were responsible for interpreting the agreement and resolving trade disputes between countries as far as possible. In other words, in the textile sector, the settlement of trade disputes had a mandatory initial phase within the AMF itself; only if this failed could recourse be made to the normal rules and procedures of the GATT, with the understanding that the recommendations issued by the AMF bodies would be duly taken into account.

SECTION II : THE PROGRESSIVE LIBERALIZATION OF TEXTILES WITH THE AGREEMENT ON TEXTILES AND CLOTHING

The ATV, which was now intended to apply to all WTO member countries and not just the forty-four signatory parties of the latest Multifibre Arrangement, was not a definitive agreement. Provisional in nature, it aimed to establish a transitional regime after which the specificities of this sectoral approach would cease and be absorbed into the general WTO regime. Naturally, it set out an implementation timetable during which the sector's traditional characteristics remained, both with regard to the safeguard clause and all institutional mechanisms.

The Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATV), integrated into the WTO and replacing the former "Multifibre Arrangements," had only a limited scope "ratione temporis." Essentially transitional in nature, it aimed to eliminate existing restrictions on international trade in covered textile products over a ten-year period, by January 1, 2005 at the latest. Moreover, any possibility of extending the ATV is excluded.³ Since that date, international trade in textiles has been subject to the general legal regime applicable to industrial products.

²CARREAU, D., JUILLARD, P. op.cit., pp 170-175

³Article 9.

The system prevailing under the AMF was based on quantitative restrictions negotiated under the aforementioned bilateral self-restraint agreements and linked to growth coefficients. To gain a comprehensive overview, all these quotas and their specific characteristics had to be notified to the Textile Supervisory Body (TSB), which then informed the member countries—that is, all WTO members, not just the forty-four that had signed the latest AMF.⁴

However, the notified restrictions were consolidated (standstill clause) as they stood. No new restrictions could be introduced in this regard, except in accordance with the general provisions of GATT 1994.⁵

This process of gradual liberalization unfolded in two concurrent and complementary phases. The first consisted, for member countries, of integrating a given and increasing percentage of their textile imports into GATT 1994.⁶: this had to be at least 16% for the first stage (January 1, 1995 to December 31, 1997), 17% for the second stage (January 1, 1998 to December 31, 2000), 18% for the third stage (January 1, 2001 to December 31, 2004), the remaining 49% having to be no later than January 1, 2005, the date of the complete integration of international trade in textile products into the "WTO System" and therefore of submission to its common law regime.

In parallel, these integration programs were assigned growth coefficients for existing quotas, with the aim of eliminating them at the end of the period, i.e., always from January 1, 2005. The principle was that during each stage, the quotas would be increased (which of course corresponds to liberalization) by a percentage equal to those established for integration under GATT 1994, plus a given annual coefficient: 0.16 for the first stage, 0.25 for the second, and 0.27 for the third.⁷In return for this planned liberalization, member countries pledged to avoid any circumvention procedures.⁸and to fight against it.

No doubt the established mechanism was quite complex but, gradually, it made it possible to ensure that at the expiry of the ATV agreement, i.e. from 1 January 2005, both the integration of textiles into the legal framework of the WTO and the elimination of all quantitative restrictions would have been achieved; the two processes being inextricably linked.

The disruption of the textile market and the need to address it through a suitable safeguard clause, more precise and operational than that provided in Article XIX of the General Agreement, remained a constant concern for the various AMFs. Such a safeguard clause remained in place on a transitional basis for the duration of the agreement.⁹Its implementation conditions are subject to numerous details regarding the parameters to be taken into consideration and especially regarding its duration.

Finally, and most importantly, any restrictions on imports could be selective and did not have to apply to all member countries under a reverse Most Favored Nation clause.¹⁰This last point was particularly important given that any selectivity is prohibited, both under the GATT and under the WTO, in the implementation of restrictive measures concerning quantitative restrictions or the safeguard clause of Article XIX. The general law of international trade thus prioritizes formal legal equality at the expense of logic and economic efficiency, formalizing a kind of Least Favored Nation clause during times of crisis. It is reasonable to argue that the selective approach to resorting to trade restrictions in times of crisis—that is, limiting them to those who cause the difficulties, a practice traditionally adopted in the past in international trade of textile products—is clearly superior from both an equity and an efficiency standpoint.

The ATV is a direct continuation of the AMF and its predecessors. The agreement was administered by its own institution, the "Textile Supervisory Body" (TSB), composed of eleven members appointed by the "Merchandise Trade Council".¹¹The new OSPT, as is traditional in this matter, was responsible for "overseeing the implementation" of the ATV; it was to this body that member countries were to send the required notifications and it was responsible for formulating observations and recommendations for this purpose.

The OSPT also played an important role in resolving trade disputes.¹²Indeed, in the first phase, the process remained purely internal to the Agreement, and it was up to the monitoring body to formulate the "appropriate recommendations" to the member countries concerned. If this failed, the parties could then, in a second phase, resort to the standard dispute settlement procedure by referring the matter to the Dispute Settlement Body (DSB) on the basis of the relevant provisions of "GATT 1994," namely Article XXIII and the Understanding on Rules and Procedures Governing the Settlement of Disputes (DSU).

However, neither yesterday under the auspices of the GATT nor today under those of the WTO has it been possible to confine textile trade disputes to this specific initial phase of conciliation.¹³

⁴Article 2, paragraphs 1 and 2.

⁵Article 2, paragraph 4.

⁶Article 2, paragraphs 6, 7, 8.

⁷Article 2, paragraphs 13 and 14.

⁸Article 5.

⁹Article 6.

¹⁰Article 6, paragraph 4.

¹¹Article 8, paragraph 1.

¹²Article 8, paragraphs 4 and 10.

¹³See GATT Rules and Practices Guide, op.cit., pp. 772-774.

In most cases, approximately 80%, difficulties were resolved within the WTO's Trade in Textiles and Apparel (TTA) and its monitoring body. However, in more sensitive cases, member countries bypassed the TTA framework and used the WTO's Dispute Settlement Mechanism (DSB). As a result, over the years, about 10% of WTO disputes have arisen from trade in textiles and apparel. In other words, the objective of the negotiating group dedicated to the problem of textiles and clothing was to reintegrate the textile sector into the framework of the GATT. Since the conclusion of the Multifibre Arrangement in 1974, the majority of trade in textile products no longer complied with the basic principles of the GATT. Developed countries, faced with imports of textile products from low-wage countries, had in fact imposed quotas on these countries, supposedly accepted voluntarily.¹⁴

The dismantling of the Multifibre Arrangement had been demanded by developing countries since 1980. Indeed, they had established their own organization, the International Textile and Clothing Bureau, which campaigned for the complete liberalization of trade in textile products.¹⁵ However, industrialized countries were very reluctant to embrace such liberalization.¹⁶

In 1982, a ministerial declaration by the Contracting Parties recognized the need to "examine the means and undertake measures aimed at liberalizing trade in textiles and clothing"¹⁷ The problems faced by the United States at that time were so great that they nevertheless pressed for an extension of the AMF in 1986.

Therefore, the dismantling of the Multifibre Arrangement was not explicitly mentioned in the Punta del Este Declaration. It simply stipulated that "negotiations in the textiles and clothing sector will aim to define modalities that would ultimately allow this sector to be integrated into the GATT on the basis of strengthened GATT rules and disciplines, thereby contributing to the achievement of the objective of increased trade liberalization."¹⁸ The extreme caution in the drafting of this paragraph clearly demonstrates the reluctance of developed countries to see barriers to trade in textile products disappear.

Negotiations on trade liberalization in the textile sector were among the most arduous. No serious negotiations on this subject began before 1989. At the mid-term conference held in Montreal in 1988, the Contracting Parties noted that no agreement yet existed in this area.¹⁹ At each stage, developed countries, particularly the United States, hindered the progress of the negotiations. Until the end of the initial phase of negotiations (December 1990), the textile sector remained one of those for which no agreement had been reached.²⁰

The negotiators considered three liberalization options. The first was to maintain the Multifibre Arrangement in force during a transitional period during which textile trade would be progressively liberalized. The second was to reform the agreement by introducing tariff quotas. The third, finally, provided for the immediate abrogation of the Multifibre Arrangement, accompanied by appropriate transitional safeguard measures.²¹

The situation was only resolved in 1991, when the Director-General of the GATT, Arthur Dunkel, on his own initiative introduced provisions relating to textiles in the "Dunkel Report" which he presented in December 1991.²² These provisions served as the basis for subsequent negotiations which ultimately led to the adoption of an agreement on textiles and clothing. It was the first solution, the gradual liberalization of the Multifibre Arrangement, that prevailed.

It should be noted immediately that the agreement on textiles and clothing was the only one to expressly provide for its eventual abrogation.²³ It ceased to have effect on January 1, 2005, at the time of the total liberalization of trade in textile products, with the exception of the rules relating to additional temporary safeguard measures which could be adopted no later than December 31, 2007. The agreement on textiles and clothing aimed for a complete liberalization of trade in textile products, within a period of ten years from 1 January 1995. The agreement expressly stipulated that the AMF should be dismantled within this period.

WTO member states were required to notify, before March 1, 1995, all bilateral self-restraint agreements in force in the textile sector.²⁴ The agreements thus notified were considered to constitute the entirety of the restrictions existing before the entry into force

¹⁴ VINCENT, P. *the WTO and developing countries*, pp. 267-275.

¹⁵ See BAGCHI, I. (1994/6). "The Integration of Textile Trade into GATT", p. 32, JWTL.

¹⁶ See the statements of the representatives of the United States and the European Community during the discussions of the Preparatory Committee tasked with determining the objectives and parameters of the Uruguay Round (doc. GATT PREP.COM(86)SR/3, p. 29 and PREP.COM(86)SR/6, pp. 31-33).

¹⁷ BIDD, sup. No. 29, pp. 11-12.

¹⁸ BIDD, supp. n° 33, p. 23.

¹⁹ See doc. GATT MTN.TNC/7 (MIN). On this point, see also BLOKKER, N., DEELSTRA, J. (1994/5). "Towards a Termination of the Multi-Fibres Arrangement?", p. 103, JWTL.

²⁰ See the Commentary on the Draft Final Act of Brussels of 1990, doc. GATT MTN.TNC/W/35/Rev.1, p. 239.

²¹ See WOLF, M. (1990). "How to Cut the Textile Knot: Alternative Modalities for Integration into GATT", in C. HAMILTON (ed.), *The Uruguay Round: Textiles Trade and Developing Countries – Eliminating the Multi-Fibre Arrangements in the 1990s*, pp. 161-180, Washington, World Bank.

²² Doc. GATT MTN.TNC/W/FA (pp. O.1 to O.36).

²³ Article 9 of the agreement.

²⁴ Article 2, paragraph 1.

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of the Agreement Establishing the WTO. All unnotified restrictions were to be repealed immediately. No new restrictions could be introduced except under the provisions of the GATT or the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing.²⁵

During the transitional period, existing restrictions could be maintained. There was no immediate abrogation of the Multifibre Arrangement. However, all trade in textile products had to be progressively brought under the rules and disciplines of the GATT.

The agreement on textiles and clothing contained a precise timetable for trade liberalization. Each WTO member was to liberalize, by January 1, 1995, the equivalent of 16% of the total volume of its 1990 imports of textile products, an additional 17% to be liberalized by January 1, 1998, a further 18% by January 1, 2002 and the remainder by January 1, 2005.

This liberalization was therefore largely spread out over time. The choice of 1990 as the reference year made it possible to further reduce its scope.²⁶

Furthermore, 49% of textile trade was only liberalized at the end of the transition period, on January 1, 2005. This high residual figure was open to criticism. If a transition period was necessary for industrialized countries, why stipulate that 49% of trade should only be liberalized in 2005, and all at once at that? Some authors even feared that developed countries might refuse to implement the final stage of liberalization so abruptly in 2005. A new transition period might have to be negotiated. The application of strict safeguard measures at that time could also not be ruled out.²⁷

The liberalization took place by categories of textiles and clothing.²⁸ Each stage had to involve products from each of the four categories set out in the agreement, namely combed and spun yarns, textiles, made-up articles and clothing.²⁹ Each member had to announce the product categories it agreed to include in the GATT disciplines at each stage. However, the agreement did not explicitly stipulate that actual liberalization had to take place at each stage, which limited the impact of the initial phases of liberalization.

With regard to sectors not yet affected by progressive liberalisation, importing Member States were required to grant their suppliers an annual increase in the growth rates contained in the bilateral self-restraint agreements.

No new restrictions could be introduced, except as provided for by the GATT or by the textiles agreement itself.³⁰

The textiles agreement, however, was unique in that it allowed for selective transitional safeguard measures. These measures were limited to imports of products not yet integrated into the domestic market. They could be taken when imports of a textile product into a Member State experienced a sudden increase, such that they caused or threatened to cause serious injury to the domestic production of similar and/or directly competing products. A significant innovation compared to the MFA was the absence of any reference to "low-priced" imports. Regardless of the price at which they were imported, textile products could only be subject to safeguard measures if serious injury or a threat of such injury was proven.

These measures were to be determined on a country-by-country basis, which fundamentally distinguished them from Article XIX of the GATT. The latter prohibits discrimination between supplier countries. Furthermore, they were not to be subject to compensation. The least developed countries and those whose exports represent only a small percentage of the imports of the member state imposing the safeguard measures were to receive more favorable treatment.

These safeguard measures could not result in a reduction of exports below their average volume during the twelve-month period ending two months before the request for consultations was initiated.³¹ They could only be adopted for a maximum period of three years or until the product in question was incorporated into the GATT.³² If the measures remained in force for more than one year, a growth coefficient of at least 6% per year had to be applied to them.³³

These safeguard measures were quite paradoxical. The objective of the textiles and clothing agreement was to eliminate existing restrictions. However, it authorized the use of additional, and moreover selective, safeguard measures.³⁴ The possibility of using these measures during the adjustment period was, however, a fundamental requirement of developed countries. They made the liberalization of the textile sector conditional upon the implementation of numerous transitional protection measures for their domestic industries.

Between 1995 and 1998, these transitional safeguard measures were applied by only two WTO members. The United States and Brazil invoked Article 6 of the agreement 26 and 7 times, respectively. In the case of the United States, two of the affected members,

²⁵Article 2, paragraph 4.

²⁶With textile trade growing every year, choosing a date far in the future made it possible to reduce the basis for calculating the volume of imports to be included.

²⁷See. BAGCHI, I. (1994/6). "The Integration of Textile Trade into GATT", p. 34, BAUGHMAN, L., MIRUS, R., MORKRE, M., SPINANGER, D. (1997). "Of Tires Cords, Ties and Tents: Window-Dressing in the ATC? », pp. 407-434, *The World Economy*.

²⁸Based on the categories of the Harmonised System for the Coding and Description of Goods developed within the Customs Cooperation Council.

²⁹Article 2, paragraphs 6 to 8 of the agreement.

³⁰Article 2, paragraph 4.

³¹Article 6, paragraph 8.

³²Article 6, paragraph 12.

³³Article 6, paragraph 13.

³⁴See. BAGCHI, I. (1994/6). "The Integration of Textile Trade into GATT", p. 34.

Costa Rica and India, initiated dispute settlement proceedings. The two panel reports³⁵ and the two reports from the Appellate Body (issued each time at the request of the complainant, it should be noted)³⁶ They considered that the United States had violated its obligations under the textile agreement. The United States had imposed a restriction on imports without demonstrating that these restrictions had caused, or actually threatened to cause, serious harm to its textile industry. The Appellate Body's report, issued at Costa Rica's request, clarified that it was no longer permissible to give retroactive effect to a restriction imposed for safeguard purposes. The United States was invited to bring the imposed restrictions into conformity with the text of the agreement, which it did. The measures imposed on imports originating in India had, in any case, already been removed, due to the decrease in imports observed elsewhere.

The other measures were examined by the Textile Supervisory Authority.³⁷ He verified the existence of harm or the threat of harm, as well as compliance with the conditions set forth, such as the growth rate. In a number of cases, he recommended that the United States cease the measures taken; which they did.

The complete liberalization of trade in textile products meant that all WTO members had to seek to improve market access. They therefore had to take measures such as lowering and consolidating tariffs, reducing or eliminating non-tariff barriers, and streamlining customs, administrative, and licensing procedures.³⁸

Developing countries had also pledged to open their markets to textile products from developed countries; this had little impact on the textile sector.

No provision in the textiles and clothing agreement stipulated that preferential treatment should be granted to developing countries, despite the importance of this sector for them. Only the preamble mentioned that special treatment should be accorded to the least developed countries.

The only application of this principle contained in the agreement was the more favorable treatment to be accorded to the least developed countries in the event of safeguard measures being taken during the transitional period.³⁹

India and Pakistan, traditionally closed countries, were unhappy about having to make commitments to open their markets. They argued that their status as developing countries should have exempted them from this obligation. Indeed, they feared it could be used by their partners, both developed and developing, as leverage for other concessions.

Part IV of the GATT could have been invoked during the Uruguay Round negotiations. However, these negotiations were marked by a return to reciprocity in the concessions made. The liberalization of trade in textile products was accepted only in exchange for a commitment from all WTO member states to open their markets to international trade. The new philosophy of international trade is that of opening the markets of all partner states. This is considered the only way to facilitate their development.

The eventual repeal of the Multifibre Arrangement did not satisfy all developing countries. Some small textile-producing countries benefited from the national quota system. This system guaranteed them a limited, but nonetheless secure, market in developed countries.⁴⁰ The complete abolition of the quota system risked leading to a monopolization of the global textile trade by a limited number of large-producing countries capable of flooding markets with cheap goods. China, in particular, comes to mind. Smaller producing countries, especially in Latin America, risked facing difficulties in finding outlets for their products.

The agreement on textiles and clothing offered a limited solution to their problem. It provided for improved access for products from Member States whose exports represented less than 1.2% of the total volume of restrictions applied by an importing Member State. This improvement was to be ensured by applying, one step ahead, the growth coefficients provided for in Article 2, paragraphs 13 and 14.⁴¹ According to the International Textile and Apparel Bureau, Peru and Sri Lanka could invoke this provision against the European Union; Colombia, Costa Rica, Jamaica, Macau, Mexico, and Uruguay against the United States; and Costa Rica, Macau, and Uruguay against Canada.⁴²

This measure did allow small-producing developing countries to temporarily acquire a slightly larger share of industrialized countries' imports. However, when liberalization was fully implemented on January 1, 2005, their exports, facing competition from Chinese exports, declined rapidly.

³⁵WTO panel reports WT/DS24/R and WT/DS33/R.

³⁶WTO reports WT/DS24/AB/R and WT/DS33/AB/R.

³⁷See the General Report of the Textiles Supervisory Body to the Council for Trade in Goods on the Implementation of the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing during the First Stage of the Integration Process, WTO Doc. G/L/179, pp. 32-45.

³⁸Article 7.

³⁹Article 6, paragraph 6.

⁴⁰See SAFADI, R., LAIRD, S.(1996). "The Uruguay Round Agreements: Impact on Developing Countries", p. 1229, World Development.

⁴¹Article 2, paragraph 18.

⁴²See International Textiles and Clothing Bureau, The Implementation of the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing, XIXth session of the Council of Representatives, 1994.

In 2004, a number of textile-producing countries, notably Turkey⁴³ presented proposals for adaptation mechanisms to be put in place in the form of supervision, or even safeguards in the event of a massive increase in exports from certain members to developed countries. China and India refused any negotiation on this subject.

This observation should not call into question the gains achieved by the abrogation of the Multifibre Arrangement. To help small textile-producing countries, however, it would have been desirable for their exports to receive preferential treatment. These countries faced the same problem in the late 1950s. How could preferential treatment be obtained within a liberalized trade system? The answer to this question in 1971 took the form of the Generalized System of Preferences (GSP). This instrument still exists. However, it does not cover the most sensitive sectors, particularly textile products. To help countries at an intermediate stage of development, it would be conceivable to include textile products in the GSPs of developed countries. This sector is where tariffs remain the highest after the conclusion of the Uruguay Round. Indeed, they average 11.1%, representing 28% of textile imports from industrialized countries, and remain subject to tariffs exceeding 15%.⁴⁴ Reducing tariffs or granting free access to textile products from small textile-producing states would allow them to export their products competitively. However, faced with the exponential increase in Chinese exports following the abolition of quotas on January 1, 2005, industrialized countries are reluctant to be generous in this regard.

From January 1, 2005, Chinese exports to the European Union doubled in a short period, with a corresponding drop in the prices of imported goods. This increase came somewhat at the expense of the EU textile industry, which had largely relocated its production, but also, as expected, primarily at the expense of other developing countries. While India, Turkey, Madagascar, and Vietnam managed to limit the damage and register a slight increase in their textile exports to the EU market (up to 25% for India), other countries saw their exports decline drastically: Myanmar by 48%, South Korea by 45%, the Philippines by 34%, Macau by 26%, Taiwan by 22%, Israel by 19%, Pakistan by 17%, Mauritius by 14%, Thailand by 12%, and Indonesia by 10%. Somewhat paradoxically, Bangladesh, designated by all observers as the big loser of liberalization, will only register a 5% loss of its market share.⁴⁵ In an equally paradoxical way, two ACP countries, subject to the same tariff conditions, Mauritius and Madagascar, performed in very different ways.

On June 10, 2005, a memorandum of understanding was concluded between the European Union and China establishing quotas on ten categories of textile products originating in China.⁴⁶ These measures were taken on the basis of Article 6 of the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing, which authorizes selective transitional measures for a maximum period of three years. Consequently, they were to end no later than 1 January 2008. They provided for quota increases of between 8% and 12.5% for 2006 and 2007.

By August 2005, quotas had been reached for several product categories. Under pressure from major retailers, the European Union agreed on August 29 to release Chinese goods that had been held up at its borders. These goods were then allocated to quotas for subsequent years.

The situation is currently stable. No further trade restrictions can be applied under the agreement on textiles and clothing. Only safeguard measures under Article XIX of the GATT are possible. However, these measures cannot discriminate between supplier countries.

CONCLUSION

This analysis reveals that the role of textiles in international trade has undergone a profound transformation, marked by a gradual shift from a highly regulated, exceptional regime to full integration into the general rules of the World Trade Organization (WTO). The Multifibre Arrangement (MFA), based on a logic of regulation and protection of developed countries' markets, long constituted a departure from the fundamental principles of free trade promoted by the GATT.

The implementation of the Agreement on Textiles and Clothing (ATV) initiated a transition towards liberalization, organized according to a phased timetable aimed at eliminating quantitative restrictions and reintegrating this sector into the multilateral system. This process, although complex and sometimes contested, culminated in 2005 with the application of general international trade rules to textile products.

However, this liberalization has not produced uniform effects. While some developing countries have benefited from open markets, others, particularly small producers, have seen their position weakened by increased competition from major exporting powers. Thus, the elimination of quotas has contributed to a restructuring of global trade, often to the detriment of the most vulnerable economies.

Therefore, the question of the fairness and efficiency of the international trading system remains. While the liberalization of the textile sector represents progress towards more open trade, it highlights the limitations of a model based on formal equality

⁴³See. communication WT/GC/W/497.

⁴⁴See. ABREU, M. "Trade in Manufactures: The Outcome of the Uruguay Round and Developing Countries Interests", in W. MARTIN., WINTERS, A. (1996). *The Uruguay Round and the Developing Countries*, pp. 66-67, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.

⁴⁵See. the table drawn by CURRAN, L. (2008). "Forecasting the Trade Outcome of Liberalization in a Quota Context – What Do We Learn From Changes in Textiles Trade Alter the ATC? », p. 137, JWTL.

⁴⁶See. EU Bulletin 6-2005, pt 1.6.23.

between states with unequal economic capacities. It thus appears necessary to rethink the support and assistance mechanisms, particularly for the least developed countries, in order to guarantee more balanced and inclusive integration into global trade.

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